

3D Graphene/Polymer Nanocomposites for Highly Sensitive and Stretchable Sensors

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The Emergence of Wearable Electromechanical Sensors

Wearable strain/pressure sensors:

Deformation of soft, curvy structures such as human body (based on electrical signals)

Typical physiological parameters:

- Heart rate;
- Respiration rate;
- Joint movements.

Health monitoring

Sport performance monitoring

Electronic skin (e-skin) for human interactive devices/robotics

Compression garments : pressure and its distribution measurement

- Conventional strain gage is metal foils and semiconductors;
- Mechanism: electrical conductance depends on the conductor's geometry.

A homogenous resistor

Square prism

$$R = \frac{\rho l}{w^2} \quad (1) \quad \frac{\Delta R}{R} = \frac{\Delta \rho}{\rho} + (1 + 2\nu)\varepsilon \quad (2) \quad \frac{\Delta \rho}{\rho} \approx 0.3 \quad (3)$$

The gauge factor (GF) :

$$GF = \frac{\Delta R/R}{\varepsilon} \approx (1 + 2\nu) \approx 1.4-2.0 \quad (4)$$

Limited detection range: 5% (maximum)

- To be used as wearable sensors

- 1) High sensitivity;
- 2) Flexibility;
- 3) High stretchability;

Bending or rotational motion associated with human joints will generate strains as high as 50%

Piezoresistive sensors based on conductive polymer nanocomposites

- ❖ Flexibility and stretchability of polymers
- ❖ High electrical conductivity of the nanomaterials

Mechanism: Resistance changes due to

- Contact resistance change
- Tunneling resistance change
- Piezoresistivity of nanomaterials (CNT)

Challenges

Direct mixing method:

- High loading of nanoparticles leads to high viscosity;
- Dispersion
- Low sensitivity: gauge factor < 2-5
- Difficulty in simultaneously achieving high sensitivity and broad sensing range.

2% CNFs in Ecoflex
Highly viscous

This project:

- **New fabrication method other than direct mixing**
- **Develop new sensors with both high sensitivity and high stretchability**

Pre-formed 3D conductive graphene networks:

I. Graphene aerogel

II. Vertical graphene

I. Graphene aerogel

Highly porous interconnected network:

- 1) Highly electrically conductive (~ 100 S/m);
- 2) Low weight density: seven time lighter than air.

Vacuum assisted infiltration:
The **conductive network of GA remains intact** and filled with PDMS.

Controlling the microstructures: pore size and pore wall thickness

GO concentration & freezing temperature

GO dispersion 1.83 to 14.5 mg/mL (freezing temperature -196 °C)

Pore size

40 μm

28 μm

18 μm

10 μm

Freezing temperature (GO dispersion 1.83 mg/mL)

Pore size

85 μm

160 μm

215 μm

350 μm

Estimation of the thickness of GA pore walls (hexagonal structure):

The density of GA can be calculated by:

$$\rho_{GA} = \frac{t}{2} \times l \times \rho_G \times 6 \times N \quad (1)$$

where ρ_{GA} and ρ_G is the density of GA and bulk graphite, respectively. N represents the number of cells per unit volume, which can be estimated by:

$$N = \frac{1}{\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{2}l^2} \quad (2)$$

Thus, the thickness of GA pore wall is estimated by:

$$t = \frac{\sqrt{3}l}{2} \frac{\rho_{GA}}{\rho_G} \quad (3)$$

GO concentration (mg/mL)	Freezing temperature (°C)	Cell size (μm)	Cell-wall thickness (μm)	Density (mg/cm ³)
1.83	-196	40 ± 5	0.037 ± 0.006	4.65
3.66	-196	28 ± 6	0.044 ± 0.011	8.15
7.00	-196	18 ± 5	0.046 ± 0.013	13.05
14.0	-196	10 ± 5	0.048 ± 0.010	24.34
3.66	-196	28 ± 6	0.044 ± 0.011	8.15
3.66	-116	85 ± 28	0.135 ± 0.021	8.09
3.66	-80	160 ± 50	0.250 ± 0.015	7.95
3.66	-50	215 ± 90	0.338 ± 0.036	7.99
3.66	-20	350 ± 100	0.550 ± 0.018	8.05

Piezoresistivity and its correlation with pore structure

GO concentration increases, GF decreases

GF increases first and then decreases upon increasing the T_{freezing}

- Larger pores result in a higher sensitivity
- Thicker pore walls lead to a lower sensitivity.

II. Vertical graphene/PDMS

Two different designs

Piezoresistivity

Monotonic Tensile Loading

- **Similar stretchability**
- **Good linearity**
- **Sandwich-structured sensors show higher sensitivity (GF)**

Cyclic Tensile Loading-durability

- **R increases upon stretching and reduces when the load is released**
- **Sandwich-structured sensors show higher durability (less drift): may be due to better load transfer**

Piezoresistivity mechanism---formation of microcracking

Cracks initiate at surface marks

Cracks propagate: longer, wider, larger number of cracks

Cracks propagate: longer, wider, larger number of cracks

Cracks close

Reload the sample, same cracks form

Thickness effects

2 μm

7 μm

13 μm

Thicker VG,
longer and wider
cracks, higher
sensitivity

Durability under water or 0.1 M NaCl (sweating)

Application demonstration

Detection of heart rate

45° bending

90° bending

Quantify the bending of finger joints

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